

Micromechanical Modelling of Novel MXene/Polymer

Nanocomposites

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Aims: Two-dimensional (2D) nanomaterials such as graphene, transition metal oxides and others are currently among the most intensively studied classes of materials that hold great promise for future applications in many science and technology areas. Recently a new family of 2D nanomaterials MXenes was discovered and opportunities of MXenes as fillers for nano-engineered structural polymer composites are very relevant. The aim of this study is to develop a finite element (FE) computational model in support of the mechanical properties optimization of polymer composite reinforced with new 2D nanoparticles MXenes.

Methods: The FE analysis was used to study the mechanical behaviour of micro structure of MXene/polymer nanocomposites. The analysis was performed by FE code DIGIMAT™ to ANSYS®. Representative volume element (RVE) models were built taking into account the properties of MXene nanosheets, as well as complex and irregular shapes of nanoreinforcements and the interaction effects between the nanofillers and the surrounding polymer matrix as these interphases have a significant influence on the mechanical properties and strength of nanocomposites.

Results: Using the developed model, the influence of MXene aspect ratio, shape, alignment and volume fraction on the mechanical properties of the polymer nanocomposite were determined. The results were verified by experimental testing.

Conclusions: FE model for mechanical properties optimization of MXene/polymer composite was proposed. The results of simulation demonstrated good agreement with experimental data.

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